

PROTEIN & DAIRY

What foods are protein?

Animal Protein: fish, seafood, chicken, turkey, eggs, cheese

Plant Protein: beans, lentils, nuts, seeds

What foods are dairy?

Dairy can be from milk, yogurt, cheese, and lactose-free milk

*Dairy foods are NOT cream cheese, sour cream, heavy cream, or butter

What about protein and dairy?

Protein feeds/builds the muscles.
Dairy provides calcium and vitamin D which is good for teeth and bones.

Want more information?

[MyPlate.gov](https://www.MyPlate.gov)

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HOMEMADE & HEALTHY Biscuits & Gravy

Biscuits & Gravy is a delicious and popular breakfast or any meal time food. We want to share a healthier way to enjoy this savory meal. Use store bought biscuits or homemade from the recipe below!

Ingredients

Gravy:

- ➔ Half pound turkey sausage
- ➔ 2 cups skim milk
- ➔ 1/4 cup flour
- ➔ 1 tsp seasoned salt and pepper to taste

Biscuits:

- ➔ 2 cups AP flour
- ➔ 1 tbsp baking powder
- ➔ 1 tsp baking soda
- ➔ 1 + 1/4 cup non-fat yogurt
- ➔ 1/2 tsp of salt

Directions

1

Preheat oven to 400°F. Combine 2 cups AP flour, baking soda, baking powder, yogurt, and salt. Fold together until combined (all dry is mixed well).

2

Using 1/4 cup, scoop out 8 drop biscuits, put onto greased sheet pan. Bake for 10-12 minutes. While biscuits are baking, begin cooking turkey sausage (brown sausage).

3

Whisk together 1/4 cup flour with 2 cups skim milk. Slowly add the milk-flour mixture to the sausage over medium heat while whisking or mixing continuously.

4

Continue to mix, and this will start thickening in a few minutes. Add 1 teaspoon of seasoning salt and 1/2 teaspoon of pepper (or to taste). Simmer another 5-10 minutes.

5

Cut biscuits in half, serve gravy over biscuits. ENJOY!

Regular Biscuits and Gravy

Serving Size: 1 biscuit about 1/2 c gravy
Calories: 540
Fat: 34g
Protein: 13g

Healthy Biscuits and Gravy

Serving Size: 1 biscuit about 1/2 c gravy
Calories: 216
Fat: 3g
Protein: 13g